

ZOOPLANKTON OF THE WETLANDS OF FEW DISTRICTS AT JHARKHAND, INDIA

*Chitra, J.

Protozoology Section, Lower Invertebrate Division, Zoological Survey of India, New Alipore, Kolkata-700 053

Article History: Received 26th May 2018; Accepted 31st May 2018; Published 20th June 2018

ABSTRACT

Planktonic forms are the producers in an aquatic ecosystem and also primary food for higher organisms. Zooplankton acts as bioindicators of the environment changes and involves in energy flow and nutrient cycling in aquatic ecosystems. They have worldwide distribution with characteristic species composition and community structure which are sensitive to changes in environment condition, nutrient enrichment and different levels of pollution. The present work embodies results of studies on the distribution, diversity and abundance of zooplankton based on the surveys of 15 major freshwater wetlands in different districts of Jharkhand, during 2009 and 2010. The investigation revealed the occurrence of altogether 40 species of zooplankton belonging to protozoa, rotifera, cladocera and copepoda. They were represented by sarcomastigophora with 4 species belongs to 3 genera, 3 families and 2 orders; Euglenozoa with 2 species belongs to 2 genera; 1 order and 1 family; Dinoflagellate of 1 species belong 1 genera, 1 order and 1 family; rotifer with 19 species belonging to 9 genera, 7 families, 2 orders; cladocera with 11 species, 9 genera, 7 families and 2 orders and copepoda with 3 species belonging to 2 genera, 2 families; and 2 orders were also recorded from the study period. Apart from zooplankton, phytoplankton, aquatic insects, mosquito larvae and nematodes were recorded during the study. Among the zooplankton, *Phacus acuminata* of Euglenozoa; *Asplanchna brightwelli*, *Brachionus angularis*, *Brachionus diversicornis* and *Brachionus caudatus personatus* of rotifera, *Ceriodaphnia cornuta* and *Pseudosida bidentata* of cladocera, cyclopoid and calanoid copepodites were found to be abundant in the freshwater wetlands. The study results are discussed in this work.

Keywords: Bioindicators, Jharkhand, Pollution, Wetlands, Zooplankton.

INTRODUCTION

The Jharkhand state is one of the newly established states of Indian union carved out of the state of Bihar in November 2000 separating 18 districts. Jharkhand shares its border with the states of Bihar to the north, Uttar Pradesh and Chattisgarh to the west, Orissa to the south, and West Bengal to the east. The state has at present 24 districts. It comprises of the Chotanagpur Plateau, which forms a part of Deccan bio-geographic province. It is a hilly undulating plateau characterized by predominantly tropical forests and tribal settlements. The total geographical area is 79,714 sq km lies between 21 58'00" N to 25 20'00" N latitude and 83 20' 00" to 87 57'00" E longitude (NWA, 2010).

Planktonic forms are the producers in an aquatic ecosystem and also primary food for higher organisms.

Zooplankton acts as bioindicators determines the environment changes, involves in energy flow and nutrient cycling in aquatic ecosystems (Fatima *et al.*, 2010). They have worldwide distribution, species composition and community structure which are sensitive to changes in environment condition, nutrient enrichment and cycling processes and involved in different levels of pollution (Holz & Hoagland, 1996; Jha & Barat, 2003; Kumar *et al.*, 2011). The present work embodies results of studies on zooplankton that reveals on the survey of 15 major freshwater wetlands at different districts of Jharkhand during 2009 and 2010. The investigation revealed a total of 40 species belonging to protista, rotifera, cladocera and copepoda. Apart from that phytoplankton, aquatic insects, mosquito larvae and nematodes were recorded during the study.

*Corresponding Author: Dr. J. Chitra Protozoology Section, Lower Invertebrate Division, Zoological Survey of India, New Alipore, Kolkata-700 053, Email: chitrajayapalan@gmail.com, Mobile: +91 9831547265

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area

Plankton samples were collected by filtering 50 L of surface water through 63 µm mesh size nylon plankton net and preserved in 4% formalin. Surface water samples were undertaken avoiding the macrophytes. Investigation was carried out qualitatively and quantitatively. Taxonomic identification of zooplankton done following the authors., (Battish, 1992; Chitra, 2013; Effler *et al.*, 1996; Khan *et al.*, 2003; Sharma & Dudani, 2013; Sharma & Sharma, 1999) and (Victor & Fernando, 1979). Quantitative enumeration of zooplankton and their constituent groups was done with a Sedgewick-Rafter counting cell.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A total of 40 species of zooplankton and phytoplankton were recorded during the study period. Among sarcomastigophora with 4 species belongs to 3 genera, 3 families and 2 orders; Euglenozoa with 2 species belongs to 2 genera; 1 order and 1 family; Dinoflagellate of 1 species belong 1 genera, 1 order and 1 family; rotifer with 19 species belonging to 9 genera, 7 families, 2 orders; cladocera with 11 species, 9 genera, 7 families and 2 orders and copepoda with 3 species belonging to 2 genera, 2 families; and 2 orders respectively from 15 localities of

various wetlands of Jharkhand respectively (Table 1). Among the 15 localities, mastigophorans and euglenoids occurrence were registered at Charwa Dam, Govindpur, Dhumka, Joraphari, Maraphari, Sholadigh and Pachamba, Girdih whereas population were abundant in Dhanbad and Bokaro districts of Jharkhand. *Ceratium hirundinella*, a dinoflagellate were also recorded from Charwa Dam at Hazaribag (Figure 1). Zooplankton is the bioindicators where their population dynamics and fluctuation states the water quality of the aquatic system. Earlier (Michael & Sharma, 1988) reported 19 species from Bihar state. (Biswas, 1966; Bohra & Kumar, 2004; Chandrasekhar & Chatterjee, 2003; Edmondson & Hutchinson, 1934; Gurney, 1907; Arvind Kumar & Gupta, 2002; Mishra & Hasan, 2013; Pandey *et al.*, 1989; Sinha & Sinha, 1983) were contributed in the studies of phytoplankton, zooplankton and physico chemical parameters from the ponds, lakes and rivers of Bihar.

The rotifer species occurrence was detected in almost in all wetlands of Hazaribag, Dhanbad, Dhumka, Koderma, Bokaro and Girdih. Bdelloid rotifers and rotifer eggs were also identified in few wetland samples. The rotifer diversity were revealed higher in the wetlands of Hazaribag and Koderma. Kumar, 1998a; 1998b; 2000 and 2001 investigated on phytoplankton, fishes, gastropods, aquatic insects and microorganisms of freshwater systems of south Bihar and Jharkhand.

Table 1. Systematic list of reported species from the wetlands of Jharkhand.

S. No.	Systematic list of the examined taxa	
	Phylum	Sarcomastigophora
	Subphylum	Sarcodina
	Class	Lobosea
	Order	Testacealobosa
	Family	Arcellidae
1.		<i>Arcella discoides</i> (Ehrenberg, 1843)
	Family	Centropyxidae
2.		<i>Centropyxis ecornis</i> (Ehrenberg, 1841 and Leidy 1879)
3.		<i>Centropyxis spinosa</i> (Cash and Hopkinson, 1905 and Deflandre, 1929)
	Family	Diffugiidae
4.		<i>Diffugia corona</i> Wallich
	Phylum	Euglenozoa
	Class	Euglenida
	Order	Euglenales
	Family	Euglenaceae
5.		<i>Phacus acuminatus</i>
6.		<i>Euglena acus</i>

	Phylum	Dinoflagellata
	Class	Dinophyceae
	Order	Gonayaulacales
	Family	Ceratiaceae
7		<i>Ceratium hirundinella</i> (Dujardin, 1841)
	Class	ROTIFERA
	Subclass	Eurotatoria (Bartos, 1959)
	Superorder	Monogononta (Wesenberg Lund, 1889)
	Order	Ploimida (Delage, 1897)
	Family	Brachionidae (Wesenberg Lund, 1899)
8		<i>Brachionus angularis</i> (Gosse, 1851)
9		<i>B. calyciflorus f. dorcas</i> (Gosse, 1851)
10		<i>B. caudatus personatus</i> (Ahlstrom, 1940)
11		<i>B. diversicornis</i> (Daday, 1883)
12		<i>B. forficula forficula</i> (Wierzejski, 1891)
13		<i>B. kostei</i> (Shiel, 1983)
14		<i>B. quadridentatus quadridentatus</i> (Hermann, 1783)
15		<i>Keratella cochlearis</i> (Gosse, 1851)
16		<i>K. lenzi</i> (Hauer, 1953)
17		<i>K. tropica</i> (Apstein 1907)
18		<i>Anaeureopsis fissa</i> (Gosse, 1851)
	Family	Euchlanidae (Bartos, 1959)
19		<i>Euchlanis dilatata</i> (Ehrenberg, 1832)
20		<i>Euchlanis incisa</i> (Carlin, 1939)
	Family	Mytilinidae (Bartos 1959)
21		<i>Mytilina ventralis ventralis</i> (Ehrenberg, 1832)
	Family	Lecanidae (Bartos, 1959)
22		<i>Lecane curvicornis</i> (Murray, 1913)
23		<i>L. leontina</i> (Turner, 1892)
	Family	Trichocercidae (Remane, 1933)
24		<i>Trichocerca diurella similis</i> (Wierzejski, 1893)
	Family	Asplanchnidae (Harring & Myers, 1926)
25		<i>Asplanchna brightwelli</i> (Gosse, 1850)
	Family	Synchaetidae (Remane, 1933)
26		<i>Polyarthra vulgaris</i> (Carlin, 1943)
	Superclass	Crustacea
	Sub-Class	Branchiopoda
	Super- order	Cladocera
	Order	Ctenopoda

	Family	Sididae (Baird, 1850)
27		<i>Pseudosida bidentata</i> (Herrick, 1884)
	Order	Anomopoda
	Family:	Daphnidae (Straus, 1820)
28		<i>Ceriodaphnia cornuta</i> (Sars, 1885)
29		<i>Daphnia carinata</i> (King 1853)
30		<i>Simocephalus vetulus</i> (Muller, 1776)
31		<i>Simocephalus exspinosus</i> (Koch, 1841)
32		<i>Simocephalus vetulus</i> (Muller, 1776)
	Family:	Bosminidae (Sars, 1865)
33		<i>Bosmina longirostris</i> (Muller, 1776)
	Family:	Moinidae (Goulden, 1968)
34		<i>Moina micrura</i> (Kurz, 1874)
	Family:	Macrothricidae Norman & Brady, 1867
35		<i>Macrothrix spinosa</i> (King, 1852)
	Family:	Chydoridae Stebbing, 1902
	Sub family:	Chydorinae Stebbing 1902
36		<i>Chydorus sphaericus</i> (Muller, 1776)
	Sub Family:	Aloninae Frey, 1967
37		<i>Alona rectangula rectangula</i> (Sars, 1862)
	Phylum	Arthropoda
	Super Class	Crustacea
	Class	Copepoda
	Order	Calanoida
	Family	Diaptomidae
38		<i>Heliodiaptomus contortus</i> (Gurney, 1907)
	Order	Cyclopoida
	Family	Cyclopidae
39		<i>Mesocyclops hyalinus</i> (Rehberg, 1880)
40		<i>Mesocyclops leuckarti</i> (Claus, 1857)

The species diversity of rotifers were logged maximum among zooplankton shows the richness viz., *Asplanchna brightwelli*, *Brachionus angularis*, *Brachionus diversicornis* and *Brachionus caudatus personatus* were found to be abundant and Koderma district recorded the higher abundance (1600 inds/m³) (Figure 1). Chandrasekhar and Chatterjee, 2003 reported 9 species of cladocerans from two lakes viz., Dimna lake and Jubilee park lakes of Jharkhand. In this study, Cladocera registered 11 species belongs to 10 genera, 7 families and 2 orders. Cladoceran cysts and neonates were also recorded during

the study. *Bosmina longirostris*, *Ceriodaphnia cornuta*, *Pseudosida bidentata* and *Moina micrura* along with cladoceran neonates were found to be dominant in Deogarh recorded about 2300 inds/m³ (Figure 2). Among copepoda, 3 species belongs to 2 genera of 2 families and 2 orders were recorded. Nauplii and copepodite stages of calanoida and cyclopoida were registered in most of the collection sites. The species abundance of copepods reached to the highest peak nearly 2600 inds/m³ at Koderma (Figure 3). Along with the zooplankton, nematodes, aquatic insects and mosquito larvae were also

noticed. Among phytoplankton, 12 species were registered from bacillariophyceae, chlorophyceae and dinophyceae. *Anabaena sp.*, *Chloropsis sp.*, *Navicula sp.*, *Chroococcus sp.*, *Closterium sp.*, *Microcystis aeruginosa*, *Pediastrum duplex*, *P. simplex*, *Synedra ulna*, *Oscillatoria sp.* and *Spirogyra sp.* were recorded from the study area. *P. duplex*

were higher in population in Koderma reached 2,300 cells/m³ and *Navicula sp.* was dominant in pond, Pachamba at Girdih (Figure 4). In overall phytoplankton and rotifers contributed higher composition followed by copepods, cladocerans and protistans.

Figure 1. Showing the abundance of Rotifera recorded at various wetlands of Jharkhand.

Figure 2. Showing the abundance of Copepoda recorded at various wetlands of Jharkhand.

Figure 3. Showing the abundance of Cladocera recorded at various wetlands of Jharkhand.

Figure 4. Showing the abundance of phytoplankton recorded at various wetlands of Jharkhand.

CONCLUSION

Studies on zooplankton in detail are meager from the water bodies of Jharkhand. Most of the freshwater bodies have shrunken due to the industrialization, human population. Existing aquatic systems are highly polluted by several sources leads to water scarcity as well non susceptibility of aquatic organism’s survival which is one of the main problem to be focussed. Proper environmental bio monitoring projects have to be undertaken to measure the status of faunal diversity. The present preliminary investigations on zooplankton occurrence were reported for the first time from the unexplored localities of Jharkhand.

Further research works have to be explored in planned sampling at regular intervals and seasonal interpretation and to correlate the physico chemical influences to infer the ecological significance of the wetlands.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

My deep gratitude to Dr. Kailash, Chandra, The Director, Zoological Survey of India for laboratory facilities and constant inspiration to pursue this study. And I extend my sincere thanks to Dr. Paliwal, Scientist B and Dr. C. K. Mondal, Assistant Zoologist for immense support in plankton collections.

REFERENCES

- Battish, S. (1992). *Freshwater Zooplankton of India*. Oxford & IBH Publishing Co. Pvt Ltd., New Delhi, India.
- Biswas, S. (1966). Five species of Daphnidae (Crustacea: Cladocera) from Simla Hills in India with a new record of *Alona costata* Sars, from Kameng Division, Nefa. *Journal of Zoological Society India*, 16, 92-98.
- Bohra, C., & Kumar, A. (2004). *Plankton Diversity in the Wetlands of Jharkhand*. Biodiversity and Environment APH Publishing Corp. New Delhi, 91-123.
- Chandrasekhar, S., & Chatterjee, T. (2003). On the collection of Cladocera from Dimna and Jublee Park Lakes, Jamshedpur, Jharkhand. *Zoos Print Journal*, 18, 1089-1090.
- Chitra, J. (2013). *Diversity, Abundance and Seasonal Fluctuation of Zooplankton from Few Wetlands In and Around Kolkata*. Records of Zoological Survey of India. 1-47.
- Edmondson, W., & Hutchinson, G. (1934). Report on Rotatoria. Article IX. Yale North India Expedition. *Connecuit Academic Arts and Science*, 10, 153-186.
- Effler, S.W., Auer, M.T., Johnson, N., Penn, M., & Rowell, H.C. (1996). Sediments *Limnological and Engineering Analysis of Polluted Urban Lake*. 600-666.
- Fatima, S. S., Rajasekhar, M. D., Kumar, K.V., Kumar, M. T.S., Babu, K.R., & Rao, C.A. (2010). Antidiabetic and antihyperlipidemic activity of ethyl acetate: Isopropanol (1: 1) fraction of *Vernonia anthelmintica* seeds in Streptozotocin induced diabetic rats. *Food and Chemical Toxicology*, 48(2), 495-501.
- Gurney, R. (1907). Further notes on Entomostraca of lower Bengal and Chota Nagpur. *Records of the Indian Museum*, 1, 21-35.
- Holz, J.C., & Hoagland, K.D. (1996). Experimental microcosm study of the effects of phosphorus reduction on plankton community structure. *Canadian Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences*, 53(8), 1754-1764.
- Jha, P., & Barat, S. (2003). Hydrobiological study of lake Mirik in Darjeeling Himalayas. *Journal of Environmental Biology*, 24(3), 339-344.
- Khan, A., Safdar, M., Khan, M.M.A., Khattak, K.N., & Anderson, R.A. (2003). Cinnamon improves glucose and lipids of people with type 2 diabetes. *Diabetes Care*, 26(12), 3215-3218.
- Kumar, A. (1998). *Biomonitoring of Pollution by Aquatic Insect Community and Microorganisms In: Freshwater Ecosystem*. Eds. A. Kumar & RK Trivedi). Enviro Media, Karad. Ecotechnology of Pollution Control & Environmental Management, 220-233.
- Kumar, A., & Gupta, H. (2002). *Ecobiodiversity of Aquatic Biota in Certain Freshwater Ecosystems of Santhal Paraganas (Jharkhand), India*. Ecology and Ethology of Aquatic Biota. Kumar, A.(Ed.), Daya Publishing House, Delhi, India, 1-69.
- Kumar, A., & Verma, P. (2001). *Ecological Status of Masanjore Reservoir in Relation to Fisheries Management in Santal Pargana (Jharkhand), India*. Ecology & Conservation of Lakes, Reservoirs and Rivers.(Ed. A. Kumar). ABD Publishers, Jaipur, 889.
- Kumar, P., Wanganeo, A., Wanganeo, R., & Sonallah, F. (2011). Seasonal variations in zooplankton diversity of railway pond, Sasaram, Bihar. *International Journal of Environmental Sciences*, 2(2), 1007-1016.
- Michael, R. G., & Sharma, B. K. (1988). Indian Cladocera (Crustacea. Branchiopoda. Cladocera). *Records of Zoological Survey of India*, 108(2), 111-122.
- Mishra, A., & Hasan, S. (2013). Assessment of water quality of Libri River, Purnia (Bihar). *International Research Journal of Science and Engineering*, 1(2), 63-68.
- NWA, (2010). Sponsored by Ministry of Environment and Forests, and Space Applications Centre. *Government of India*, 1-170.
- Pandey, B., Hussain, S., & Jha, A. Shyamanand, 2004. Seasonal fluctuation of zooplankton community in relation to certain parameters of river ramjan of kishanganj, Bihar. *Nature, Environment and Pollution Technology*, 3(3), 325-330.
- Rai, D., & Sharma, U. (1989). Zooplankton periodicity in weed infested wetlands of north Bihar. *Journal of Freshwater Biology*, 1(2), 161-166.
- Sharma, B., & Dudani, V. (2013). Rotifers from some tropical ponds in Bihar: species composition, similarities and trophic indicators. *Journal of the Indian Institute of Science*, 72(2), 121.
- Sharma, B., & Sharma, S. (1999). Freshwater Rotifers (Rotifera: Eurotatoria). *State Fauna Series: Fauna of Meghalaya*, 4(9), 11-161.
- Sinha, K., & Sinha, D. (1983). Seasonal trends in physico-chemical factors and zooplankton in a freshwater pond of Munger, Bihar. *Journal of Ecobiology*, 5(4), 299-302.
- Victor, R., & Fernando, C. (1979). The freshwater ostracods (Crustacea: Ostracoda) of India. *Records of the Zoological Survey of India*, 74(2), 147-242.